

Trends in Pediatric Palliative Care Research – Visuals and Analysis of Trends in 2023

Colleen Pawliuk, Research Librarian

Candice Barrans, Parent Partner

Department of Pediatrics, BC Children's Hospital

Abstract:

This commentary is a look back at the citations published in 2023. We share this data in the hopes of informing the pediatric palliative research community with some analytics of the publication trends in pediatric palliative research, including top journals, top authors, and top funders, as well as visualizations of networks for index terms, co-authorship, and organizations.

This commentary is a part of the Trends in Pediatric Palliative Care Research commentary series. To learn more or to sign up for our monthly newsletter visit: <https://pediatricpalliative.com/research-blog/>

To see the visualization live and have the ability to view them full-screen, read this commentary on our website: <https://pediatricpalliative.com/trends-in-pediatric-palliative-care-research-visual-and-analysis-of-trends-in-2023/>

Trends in Pediatric Palliative Care (TPPCR) aims to concentrate relevant research on Pediatric palliative care propel the fields latest developments to the community, while adding depth and perspective to the literature via personal commentaries which reflect lived experience as clinicians, researchers, trainees and parent partners.

In 2023 we realized this through the publication of 16 newsletters, including special editions in oncology, low resource settings and 3 parent perspective commentaries. Our readership has exceeded 1,000 direct subscribers with over 200 subscriptions in 2023, with 42% of these subscribers being highly engaged with our newsletter. 75% of our readership is from the US, Canada, and the UK, 25% are from other communities around the world.

Below is a look back at the citations published in 2023. We share this data in the hopes of informing the pediatric palliative research community with some analytics of the publication trends in pediatric palliative research, including top journals, top authors, and top funders, as well as visualizations of networks for index terms, co-authorship, and organizations.

Methods

All papers [included in our 2023 lists](#), including special issues (n=409), were searched for in Scopus. Paper that were not indexed in Scopus could not be retrieved (n=30), and so we were left with a total of 379 papers for this analysis. [VOSviewer](#) was used to create the citation network visualizations and [Tableau Public](#) was used to create all other visualizations.

Top Journals

Top Authors

The authors with 4 or more papers on our 2023 lists were:

- [Joanne Wolfe](#) – 9 Papers
- [Justin N. Baker](#) – 8 Papers
- [Jori F. Bogetz](#) – 6 Papers
- [Erica C. Kaye](#) – 6 Papers
- [Lisa C. Lindley](#) – 6 Papers
- [Melanie J. Cozad](#) – 5 Papers
- [Sarah Friebert](#) – 5 Papers
- [Daniel H. Grosseohme](#) – 5 Papers
- [Jessica Keim-Malpass](#) – 5 Papers
- [Radion Svyrenko](#) – 5 Papers
- [Megan Doherty](#) – 4 Papers
- [Lorna K. Fraser](#) – 4 Papers
- [Pamela S. Hinds](#) – 4 Papers
- [Ricardo Martino-Alba](#) – 4 Papers
- [Adam Rapoport](#) – 4 Papers
- [Gwendolyn Richner](#) – 4 Papers
- [Jennifer Snaman](#) – 4 Papers
- [Johanna Taylor](#) – 4 Papers
- [A. A. Eduard Verhagen](#) – 4 Papers

Top Funders

Below are the top funding organizations for 2023 that have funded 4 or more studies on our list.

Indexed Terms Network

This citation network shows the frequency and connection between indexed term. To be included in the visualization an indexed term must appear at least 5 times. To view the network of a specific keyword, click on the node or hover your mouse over the node for 2 seconds.

Organizational Networks

This visualization shows the organizations of the authors contributing to research in the field and the networks between them. To be included in this visualization an organization must appear at least twice.

